

ORION | Trapezium

A Monthly Publication of the ORION Astronomical Society

This shows three images of 3I/ATLAS, the 3rd identified interstellar object, recorded at TAO at different times on the evening of 18 Aug 2025. The black lines show the path predicted by JPL Horizons for the two-hour periods 9-11 pm 18 Aug and 12-2 am 19 Aug 2025 (the times are Eastern). The lower left insert shows the first image of 3I/ATLAS (red circle) in a stack of 7 60-sec frames, midpoint 10:05 pm. The upper right insert shows the next image, a stack of 14 4-sec exposures from the Meade-LX200, midpoint 11:09 am (white circle). Finally, the central image shows the trail of 3I/ATLAS in a 16-min stack, 11:14 - 11:30 pm (bold arrow). For more information see the 18 Aug 2025 Dark Stargaze discussion in this issue.

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Page Three Astronomy

Evidence for Alien Life:

3I/ATLAS imaged at TAO

ORION Monthly meeting, 20 Aug 2025.

The **ORION Astronomical Society** is a science and astronomy group founded in April 1974 by scientists from the United States Department of Energy facilities at Oak Ridge, Tennessee. We primarily serve the communities of Oak Ridge and Knoxville and the counties of Anderson, Knox, and Roane.

ORION's mission is to support scientific research, teaching, and astronomical activities in East Tennessee. We hold monthly public meetings at the Oak Ridge RSCC Campus, and are active at Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO), hosting public events, sharing knowledge of the skies, and helping to provide intellectually stimulating programs. ORION works to share the wonders of the cosmos and the culture of science.

ORION members include scientists, engineers, technicians, IT experts, artists, students, and others with varied talents and expertise. Over half of ORION members own telescopes, many are amateur radio operators, and some have expertise in astrophotography.

ORION has working relationships with several organizations, including museums and other amateur astronomy groups. Membership is open to individuals who will actively contribute their time and ideas. The annual membership fee is \$20, and student discounts are available. There is no charge for our newsletters and publications, or for participation in most ORION activities.

ORION Board and Officers:

President: Don Spong

VP and Program Chair: David Fields

Social Chair: Noah Frere

Secretary: Rob Fowler

Treasurer: Bob Edwards

Editor: Ted Barnes

Astrotechnologist: Rob Scott

Videographer: Rob Fowler

Obed Site Outreach: Joshua Gray.

TRAPEZIUM is a monthly publication of the ORION Astronomical Society. The issue date is the Friday preceding the monthly ORION meeting, chosen to provide timely information regarding the planned Program.

From March 2025 we will be working towards issuing a somewhat shorter version of the Trapezium, which will still include important information regarding the monthly ORION presentation, as well as dates and other information regarding Public Stargazes and other notable events relating to ORION and TAO.

Regarding the contents of this revised Trapezium, we have already concluded that some components, such as a separate Astrophotography section, are so important for a publication on amateur astronomy that one really cannot justify excluding them.

Messages from ORION

September begins the transition from summer to fall, and should provide some good viewing opportunities as we encounter dryer weather and longer nights. I was away for two weeks in September, visiting my daughter and family in San Francisco. While there I was able to attend the September meeting of the San Francisco Amateur Astronomers ([sfaa-astronomy dot org](http://sfaa-astronomy.org)), and heard an interesting lecture on solar probes and solar physics. They do many of the same things that we do (monthly programs, outreach events, Stargazes), but on a larger scale.

Congratulations to the occultation team for recent successful double occultation imaging on the evening of Sept. 7. See further details in articles in this issue, *e.g.* pp. 54-63. In September the New Moon is Sept. 22, with Sept. 20-21 being a promising dark-sky weekend. The Full Moon (known as the Corn Moon this month) was on Sept. 8. Saturn and Neptune are starting to be visible in the evenings. The Sun remains very active, and provides interesting views (sunspots, prominences), but be sure you have the right solar filters ($H\alpha$, Ca-K, or white light). There is one object of particular interest, recently imaged by ORION members, the interstellar visitor 3I/ATLAS, but it is currently at the quite faint magnitude of 16.5. For more information, see [cometchasing dot skyhound dot com](http://cometchasing.skyhound.com). 3I/ATLAS will not be at closest approach to Earth until Dec. 19. No meteor showers this month, but the Orionids will be here in October. With respect to deep sky objects there are still many opportunities. The constellation Cygnus is a good source of targets, for example the Eastern and Western Veil nebulas, the Crescent nebula, and several star clusters. The Cat's Eye Nebula (NGC 6543) is in good position in the constellation Draco, and the Dumbbell Nebula (M27) is a popular target in Vulpecula. The great globular cluster in Hercules (M13) is also in good position now – visible with binoculars. M57 (the Ring Nebula) is in the constellation Lyra, opposite the star Vega, and is a good target for both observing and imaging. The Lagoon (M8) and Trifid (M20) Nebulas are also good for imaging now (see my M20 image in *Astrophotography*, p.68). Of course, if you can get to a good dark sky site, this is also still a great time to see the Milky Way.

TAO Director's Message / Observatory Way

David Fields

September 2025

The photo on the left shows our new road sign for Roane State's Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO). Traveling West on Caney Creek Road from Roane County Park, the sign appears on the left just after crossing Joiner Hollow Road.

TAO Public Stargazes and Special Events

TAO offers Public Stargazes to the community on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month, weather permitting. Our usual schedule for the summer is to open at 8:30 pm and continue to nominally 10:30 pm -- later when the sky and attendance encourage this. Opening time changes according to the season, and a good guide is to arrive at the observatory about sunset, when weather is encouraging. These Stargazes are supported by local astronomy clubs, especially ORION members and friends, and benefit our students and community. Our TAO Stargazes are usually well attended, with a full classroom of visitors for evening astronomy lectures.

A month of excitement: An Interstellar Visitor

TAO has had an exciting month. First (in every way), 3 groups of our astronomers managed a significant accomplishment, in getting photos of **3I/ATLAS**, the third confirmed interstellar object, now passing through our skies. This interstellar visitor is quite faint, and capturing it photographically was a triumph of planning, together with a light-bucket of luck. It was a first for all of us, a first for TAO, and perhaps a first instance of several people all managing to capture this very significant and difficult celestial object.

At our Monday board meeting on August 18 we discussed **3I/ATLAS**, and Ted pointed out that although it was not close to Earth, it might now be bright enough to image, and was in an accessible part of our sky. We recognized that on that evening skies were very clear, and the moon was below the horizon. Several of us decided to visit TAO that evening and try to obtain photos. The first photo to be analyzed was Ted's (left image, following page), the second Richard's (right image, first attempt at analysis) and the third Rob's/David's. Each image showed the elusive interstellar visitor!

TAO Director's Message / Observatory Way (cont.)

Identifying the exotic interstellar visitor 3I/ATLAS in our TAO images.

The complete story, a third image showing all of the photos combined (see the cover image), and the conclusions appear elsewhere in this issue of the Trapezium; see esp. pp.39-50. 3I/ATLAS was discovered by an observatory in Chile, partially funded by NASA through the ATLAS early asteroid warning Collaboration. But NASA projects, along with many research, health-related, educational, and (all) climate-related activities, are being diminished (some say destroyed) by our current government. More research is being left to private individuals, industry, and to universities with their diminished funding.

TAO Director's Message / Observatory Way (cont.)

A month of excitement: Students, IF Stargaze

TAO Astronomers support our Astronomy Classes, our Public Stargazes, and our Special Events. Examples of special events are eclipses, planetary transits across the sun, and Asteroid Occultations. A recurring special event is our monthly "International Friendship Stargaze" which is held during the week of the first quarter moon at the Bissell Park "International Friendship Bell" in Oak Ridge.

We welcome our Fall 2025 Astronomy students, who participated in our Aug. 28 International Friendship Stargaze. This image shows our RSCC Fall Astronomy students plus on the back row (R) our younger visitors, and on the front row (L), Astronomy Instructor Noah Frere.

TAO Director's Message / Observatory Way (cont.)

A month of excitement: Moon Madness

Our first-Saturday monthly Stargaze (nominally Sept. 6) was clouded out, so we announced a postponement date of Sunday Sept. 7. This was a fun event. Don Spong celebrated the Moonrise over the trees by a few moon music solos (with recorded backup).

In the classroom, Don (below L) showed his photo of a supernova shining brightly in a distant galaxy. Ted (below R) discussed the astrophotography setup that he used for his photos of interstellar object 3I/ATLAS (see writeup above, and elsewhere in this issue of the Trapezium, especially pp.39-50). David welcomed our enthusiastic visitors and discussed our TAO activities. It was a great evening.

TAO Director's Message / Observatory Way (cont.)

Atmospheric Gravity Waves at TAO

We occasionally see atmospheric gravity waves at TAO. Gravity waves are a visible manifestation of (otherwise invisible) atmospheric gravity waves. These can be seen from TAO as wave-like cloud formations that appear when westerly air masses cross the Cumberland Plateau. They appear as parallel, rippling bands in the sky, much like the ripples that form when a stone is dropped into a pond. I captured this photo at TAO on August 16; the photo shows two bands crossing the western sky. I occasionally see a single band crossing the sky from horizon to horizon, competing with the Milky Way. Here these were interrupted by a (mostly) vertical storm feature.

Dramatic atmospheric interactions to the West of TAO.

TAO Director's Message / Observatory Way (cont.)

And finally ... New Oak Ridge AMSE Display

We have a new, inspiring Astronomy display at the American Museum of Science and Energy! Please visit AMSE and have a personal look at our multi-dimensional display!

ORION @ AMSE

ORION Board Meetings ElCantarito

- Rob Fowler

This is a summary of topics discussed recently at the weekly (Monday 1 pm) ORION Board Meeting held as a regular working lunch at ElCantarito restaurant in Oak Ridge. Notes as contributed in Stardate format by Sec. Rob Fowler.

Stardate: 2025.03.31

In attendance were Robert Fowler, Ted Barnes, David Fields, Art Alison and Don Spong. Discussed delays on new dome report due to committee participant availability. Discussed possible going to TAO Tuesday night. Discussed next speaker is not firm for April's meeting. Discussed voting for officers at the next ORION Meeting. Discussed the next Friendship Stargaze and date for same, 8th possibly. Discussed possibly coming up with cloudy night entertainment for Friendship stargaze. Discussed Wordsworth poem about telescopes. Discussed potential security cams for TAO.

Stardate: 2025.04.07

In attendance were David Fields, Art Alison, Ted Barnes and Rob Fowler. Ted discussed the data acquired from his Arduino/LED test. David discussed a mount having the ability to track asteroids via PHD2. David discussed the Friendship Stargaze is 7:30pm Tuesday. Discussed needing pics of new concrete pads at TAO.

Stardate: 2025.04.14

In attendance were David, Ted, Art and Rob. Ted discussed results of the 785 Zwetana occultation. After a long and dramatic story, Ted revealed a successful capture. Noah is reaching out to Joe Baldwin about next month's presentation. Ted discussed quantum field theory using functional methods.

Stardate: 2025.04.21

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Art Alison, Noah Frere and Rob Fowler. Ted discussed how to use AnyDesk and log in unattended. Ted discussed a planetary occultation, Mars vs a 9th magnitude star on May 6th at 1 am. David discussed progress he is making with a Meshtastic receiver. Mention of 4 visitors who showed up at TAO and new member Kevin Wilson. David brought up calendar access .Discussed problem with rotation of glow dome lid. Watch for migration of wheel axles. One axle migrated in and caused the lid to bind.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Stardate: 2025.04.28

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Art Alison, Kevin Wilson, John Cliff and Rob Fowler. Briefly mentioned domes on CloudyNights.com. Ted discussed upcoming Mars/Star occultation and relevant challenges. HD 74058 vs Mars just after midnight 00:44 night 5th/6th morn. TAO Stargaze beginning at May 3rd 8pm. Friendship Stargaze possibly May 6th. Briefly discussed avoiding Feynman's van. Shared astrophotos. Discussed potentially going to TAO tonight & Noah's class.

Stardate: 2025.05.05

In attendance were David Fields, Art Alison, Ted Barnes, Kevin Wilson, and Rob Fowler. David asked if we have a set program for May. That remains unclear. Ted contacted Noah to confirm. We await a reply. Ted mentioned the next annual IOTA meeting is possibly going to be in New Mexico in Oct.

Stardate: 2025.05.12

At 11am David, Ted & Art met at the Library and made a first pass as setting up a display case for the club. Rob joined later. It was artistically done, decorated with a small telescope, some antique books, and astrophotos. Discussed whether Kevin might give the May lecture and what topics he has ready. He agreed to speak on the topic of stellar spectroscopy. Ted mentioned the next possible occultation on the early morning on 5/21/2025.

Stardate: 2025.05.19

In attendance were Don, David, Ted, Art, Kevin, and Rob. Kevin brought up Benjamin Baniker as a potential lecturer. Rob announced that the most recent lecture is on YouTube.

Star Date: 2025.05.26

In attendance were Don, Dave, Art & Rob. David suggested improvements to the Meade's power supply in hopes of reducing noise, higher amperage power supply, adding ferrite cores. Dave discussed getting a construction party to begin construction on the Dob shelter. Discussed parking issues at TAO.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Stardate: 2025.06.02

In attendance were Don, David, Bob, Art, Juan, Kevin and Noah (and Sunny). We met early at the library to discuss the current and new display box. Discussed meeting again, tomorrow (Tuesday). David suggested Wednesday night 8:30pm as the next Friendship Stargaze. Kevin suggested meeting at TAO to look at the Meade's encoder. Noah suggested reaching out to Gareth Davis to see if he has any potential acquaintances for another lecture. Don asked about the new dome project. David responded with a tale of woe regarding the Roane purchasing project.

Stardate: 2025.06.09

In attendance were Don, David, Art and Rob (joined by John Rather). David purchased 2 coin cells for the Celestron CGM mount. He also purchased a few ferrite cores to suppress noise from the power supply. Ted expressed an interest in having help with this months Trapezium. Discussed the new optical telescope coming online in the Atacama Desert. Briefly mentioned the library displays and Oak Ridge street lighting. Noah mentioned that Gareth Davis can give the next lecture.

Stardate: 2025.06.16

In attendance were Don, Kevin, Art and Rob. Rob showed his submission for the AMSE poster. Kevin & Don discussed PixInsight. We confirmed Kevin is speaking this month. Kevin discussed the Astronomical League and it's various programs, and contests for various achievements.

Stardate: 2025.06.23

Due to crowding at the table, no notes were taken. In attendance were Don, David, Ted, Art, Kevin and Robert.

Stardate: 2025.06.30

In attendance were David, Ted, Art, Kevin, and Rob. Don sat in for a short while. Ted & Rob discussed results of the occultation via a new process. Kevin presented a new ORION Logo. Kevin announced he will be moving out of the immediate area.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Stardate: 2025.06.30 (cont.)

David presented Kevin with a gift ORION T-Shirt. David brought up shop type measurements he intends to do on the Meade. The group went on discuss various theoretical topics. Mention of 4 visitors who showed up at TAO and new member Kevin Wilson David brought up calendar access. Discussed problem with rotation of glow dome lid. Watch for migration of wheel axels. One axel migrated in and caused the lid to bind.

Stardate: 2025.07.07

In attendance were Don, Ted, David, Art, Rob and visitor John Rather. Conversations opened with Ted discussing digitizing the occultation substacking project. David discussed a lightstrip project and possible application in the dome. Ted collected info for this month's Trapezium. David discussed attendance at the Sat July 5 Public Star Gaze, was 12, give or take. David discussed the testing we did on the Meade and saw no alignment errors.

Stardate: 2025.07.14

In attendance were David, Ted, Art and Rob. Ted shared some mathematical analysis of the recent occultation data. David brought up potential dates for the next Friendship Star Gaze. We discussed the next ORION lecture and whether to zoom it or not. We discussed possibly having a news feature at ORION lectures.

Stardate: 2025.07.21

In attendance were David, Don, Ted, Art, Rob... and guest John. Dave led the discussion with Rob's absence. Dave mentioned that Saturday night's public star gaze was successful, with around 8 visitors. We discussed the recent lecture and the unplanned move to the computer classroom. The general consensus is that it went well. Dave will be away on August 2nd, the next star gaze. Ted brought up details of participation in the Tuesday night / Wednesday morning occultation.

Stardate: 2025.07.28

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Art Alison and Rob Fowler We will probably have a public star gaze at TAO on 8/2/2025, public or private depending on weather and Noah's decision. 8/12/2025 Perseid meteor shower a probable star gaze.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Stardate: 2025.07.28 (cont.)

Our Library display will expire soon. David will inquire if we can keep it another month or if we need to clean it out this month. If it has to come down, Ted & Rob have agreed to remove the contents.

Stardate: 2025.08.04

Present were Don, Ted, Rob, Art and guest John Rather. Ted shared his most recent results and submission to IOTA that we have been re-evaluating. Don won't be present for the August ORION meeting. We believe John Cliff is August's speaker. We discussed various lightning phenomenon We also discussed the Big Bang theory and John Rather's book.

Stardate: 2025.08.11

Present were Don, Ted, David, Art, Rob and guests Richard Piety and John Rather. Ted reported on some of his recent results with IOTA's python scripts and graphing. Rob reported on visiting Lily Bluff's Star Party at Wartburg, where he met Joshua, Gareth and Owen. Don told us of a new 16 bit color astro camera he just bought, a ZWO ASI2600MCP. John told us of an experience with a pro telescope. Richard just bought a QHY174M-GPS camera for recording timed asteroid occultations. We discussed weather regarding the Perseid meteor / stargaze, 8:30pm Tuesday, but the weather is deteriorating. There is a possible occultation on 8/23/25.

Star date: 2025.08.18

In attendance were Ted, David, Art, Rob and guests John Rather and Richard Piety. David spoke to Courtney at AMSE about our ORION display. We have been invited to keep it set up for a while longer. We discussed possibly tracking 3I/ATLAS to get a pic, having an unscheduled observation evening.

Star Date: 2025.08.25

In attendance were Dave, Ted, Richard and Rob. Ted shared the results of the recent asteroid occultation. David visited the K-25 interpretive center and described the layout. He said they are interested in us bringing a star party to that location. David noticed that one of the new pads in collecting water. Rob suggested a modified a port-a-potty as a camouflage telescope cover. Calling it "Astro-Johnny: Smelling like Roses!"

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Star Date: 2025.09.01

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Art Alison and Rob Fowler. And visitor David Allred. David Fields fixed the internet with at TAO and treated several ant colonies. The skies were good from 9pm to Midnight. Discussed an upcoming eclipse in Sydney Australia in 2 years. Ted spoke to the programmer of Occult Watcher [Hristo Pavlov] who helped him troubleshoot a bug. IOTA Annual meeting is next week on zoom.

Star Date: 2025.09.08

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Rob Fowler, Don Spong, Art Alison and Richard Piety. We has a successful Moon-gaze at TAO last night. Ted discussed his occultation studies. He was successful with one last night Sunday 2025.09.07. Richard attempted it too but has not analyzed his results yet. We had a new guest last night, Art's friend Deirdre Akin. She joined the astro-luncheon as well.

ORION Monthly Meetings

ORION Monthly Meeting Format

Meeting Venue: City Room (A-111), just inside the main entrance, Coffey/McNalley Bldg., Oak Ridge Campus, Roane State Community College.

7:00 pm Eastern, 3rd Wednesday of each month.

Our monthly meetings (except for December, a dinner) generally proceed as follows:

- Welcome
- Announcements
- Invited Presentation and Discussion
- Awarding of the Mug
- Astrophotography / Special Presentations

The nominal start time is 7:00 pm Eastern, on the 3rd Wednesday of the month. The beginning of the meeting will usually include announcements of general interest.

Meetings typically continue until around 9:00 pm. Please plan to stay until the end. Hopefully we will all enjoy the astrophotography and other special topics discussed in the latter part of the meeting.

Remote Viewing: A live Zoom session will usually be open during the ORION Monthly Meeting, at the link:

<https://us02web.zoom.us/j/88528735960?pwd=KzY4bnBHcjltZg3L3pOcjY0TFovUT09> or
<https://bit.ly/42apGxX>

Meeting ID: 885 2873 5960 Passcode: 716689

Title: The Lightest and Heaviest Elements and their Isotopes as Powerful Groundwater Tracers

Speaker: Gareth Davies

Abstract:

Tracers are labels that make fingerprints in substances so they can be identified in a system. In terms of groundwater, types of tracers include implicit assumptions that make a resulting model. There is the often used model of an isotropic and homogeneous system with strict assumptions, that typically departs from reality as soon as any field data (and tracer data) are collected. Injected tracers are deliberately added to a system, with a fundamental assumption that they can be identified within or as they exit the system. Chemical tracers are within the system (*e.g.*, surface or groundwater) that have patterns that can be recognized as input or output fingerprints. Isotopic tracers have fingerprints that include naturally radioactive and stable elements. Two of the primordial elements and their isotopes (H and He) are the lightest and useful tracers. In addition, the heaviest natural element U and its isotopes are very useful and powerful tracers. Uranium and certainly the transuranic elements Np, Pu, Am and Cm are very useful as tracers in the nuclear industry (and in groundwater). It is fascinating that the lightest natural isotopes ^1H and ^2H (deuterium) are as fundamentally useful as the heaviest, U and its daughters. What is really useful about radioactive isotopes as tracers is that as they decay they become different elements that have

Abstract (cont.):

different chemical properties, but can be used as sensitive tracers themselves. The most useful results arise from using multiple tracers in a system because they cover the issues of conservative and nonconservative behavior in a system and provide the most useful information. Models are typically used and there has to be some way to test them - those tests must not be bounded by the same assumptions as the model, and tracers facilitate that. Almost all the periodic table has formed in stars, H is truly primordial, and U is formed by colliding neutron stars or black holes. These tracers are really special.

Mini Bio:

From high school in South Wales, UK, Gareth became interested in mountains and caves and was soon led into sampling cave water, doing lab chemistry, and tracing groundwaters with fluorescent dyes as part of a cave research project. After serving in the Royal Air Force and working as an air traffic controller in civilian aviation, he moved to the US. He received a B.S. (Geology) at Millsaps College in 1984, and an M.S. at the University of Southern Mississippi in 1987 (Geology), finally finishing a karst-related thesis on uranium-series dating of speleothems from two caves in Tennessee. He has worked in a variety of geological settings from the tropical karst of Southeast Asia to crystalline rocks in the U.S. Rocky Mountains, has authored / co-authored more than 50 publications, and is a Fellow of the Geological Society of America.

ORION Last Month

Geochemical Evidence for Life on Mars

- *John Cliff*

Our featured speaker for the August 2025 ORION Presentation on 20 Aug was ORION member and ORNL Scientist John Cliff. John addressed the early history of the Earth and Mars, and reviewed the various chemical and isotopic signatures that have been suggested as possible ways to identify evidence for Martian life. This topic was of considerable interest to the audience, who were clearly fascinated by the subject, and had many questions for John and for other audience members. One interesting concern John raised was a tendency for investigators to be very skeptical about possible evidence for Martian life that would readily be accepted as valid for a similar situation on Earth.

John prepares to address our sizeable audience of Mars aficionados.

ORION Last Month

Geochemical Evidence for Life on Mars (cont.)

ORION VP David Fields thanks John Cliff for his exciting and detailed presentation on the status of Geochemical Evidence for Life on Mars.

ORION Last Month

Geochemical Evidence for Life on Mars (cont.)

“If you believe that the geochemical evidence presented here implies the existence of life on Mars, please raise your hand.”

Events and Calendars, Sky Maps and Occultations

Star, Moon, Comet and Meteorgazing at TAO in 2025

We enthusiastically invite visitors to attend our Public Stargaze events, held at our dark-sky site, the Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO) near Kingston, Tennessee. These events are intended especially for visitors, so our buildings and facilities will be open, and there will be astronomy talks as well as public skywatching.

In Jan-Jun 2025 we plan to hold fixed-calendar public Stargaze events on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month. These weekend events are especially appropriate for families. We also hold public special events, such as a “Full Moonrise,” with associated Moon Music, and the occasional comet watch. The annual Perseid Meteor watch in mid-August is especially popular.

The precise dates of many of these events depend on the local weather conditions, and cannot be specified *definitively* long in advance. As an approximate guide, see the TAOCalendar pages following. Once a date is finalized we usually confirm it through the ORION online message site ORION astronomy@groups.io. Likely and unlikely dates for TAO events may be inferred from the weather predictions at TAO by Clear Sky Charts (cleardarksky dot com) and Astrospheric (astrospheric dot com).

Please confirm event dates before proceeding to TAO.

In view of the rather challenging approach road to TAO, “Observatory Way,” first-time visitors should plan to arrive before dark. Driving instructions are given at: <https://www.roanestate.edu/pages/obs/visit.htm>

Some instructions follow, since people may be unfamiliar with procedures for stargazing at a dark-sky site.

ORION members are invited to arrive early with their telescopes and mounts, to prepare for evening observing and to share refreshments. Please bring a red flashlight, or a headband with a red-light option.

Visitors who wish to acquire red lights or red-light headbands for observing may find them at many commercial amateur astronomy sites, such as [https:// www dot high pointscientific dot com](https://www.highpointscientific.com). The “Lepro LE” LED Headlamp, model 3200008, available from Amazon for about \$10 (Aug. 2024) is a personal favorite. This is rechargeable and has separate red and white led buttons, with several brightness settings. A caution: For amateur astronomy, brighter lights are NOT preferred, and WHITE lights are highly discouraged. Please use only red lights while the Stargaze is in progress.

Parking is available on site; on entering TAO **stay to the right**, and *please use the parking area below and right (Southwest) of the TAO buildings and observing area, near the treeline*. And **PLEASE NO HEADLIGHTS ON SITE.**

Visitors are encouraged to interact with ORION astronomers who have set up and may be operating telescopes and other astronomical equipment. We enjoy public discussions, and regard this sharing of information as a primary goal of our organization. Visitors are welcome to coffee and other refreshments.

TAO Public Stargazing: A Note Regarding Scheduling and Access in 2025

In 2025 we are reverting to an earlier schedule of having our Public Stargaze nights on every first and third Saturday. Of course this assumes good weather; if the weather is not suitable, a changed schedule will be announced on the group site [ORIONastronomy @ groups.io](https://groups.io/g/ORIONastronomy).

We decided that the previous (2024) schedule of a once-monthly Public Stargaze was insufficient, and having a Moon visible in some phase other than close to New gives our visitors an obvious and interesting object for viewing.

During Daylight Savings Time (mid-March through early November) we plan to hold our Public Stargaze events over the hours of approximately 8:00 pm - 11:00 pm, with some nominal variation.

If it is already dark when you arrive, please dim your headlights on the TAO grounds, follow the right branch of the access road, and park to the right of the TAO building, near the treeline.

Note: Parking in or near the elevated flat observing area at the front (East) of the TAO building is reserved for astronomers who are bringing their equipment.

Additional information for visitors may be found on the previous page and following two pages of this issue.

TAO Public Stargazes in September: Sats 06 & 20 Sep 2025

Sat 06 Sep 2025

Sunset	7:59 pm
Civ dusk	8:25 pm
Ast dusk	9:27 pm
Moonrise	7:33 pm
Moonset*	7:00 am
	*07 Sep

Moon illum. 98%

Waxing Gibbous Moon
Nearly Full Moon during this event.

Sat 20 Sep 2025

Sunset	7:39 pm
Civ dusk	8:04 pm
Ast dusk	9:05 pm
Moonrise	6:10 am
Moonset	7:09 pm

Moon illum. 2%

Waning Crescent Moon
No Moon visible during this event.

TAO Public Stargazes in October: Sats 04 & 18 Oct 2025

Sat 04 Oct 2025

Sunset	7:18 pm
Civ dusk	7:44 pm
Ast dusk	8:43 pm
Moonrise	5:58 pm
Moonset*	5:46 am
	*05 Oct

Moon illum. 91%

Waxing Gibbous Moon
Nearly Full Moon during this event.

Sat 18 Oct 2025

Sunset	6:59 pm
Civ dusk	7:25 pm
Ast dusk	8:25 pm
Moonrise	5:03 am
Moonset	5:37 pm

Moon illum. 8%

Waning Crescent Moon
No Moon visible during this event.

TAO Calendars

Jan-Jun 2025; Aug & Sep 2025

The principle public events for visitors at TAO are the **Public Stargazes**, held at TAO during 2025 on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month. These are listed in the “**Public Fixed Events**” **TAO Calendar** for six month periods, currently Jul-Dec 2025. These appear on the page following.

Additional notable events will be included in monthly “**Special Events**” **TAO Calendars**. These include public events that do not have a fixed date long in advance, such as the **International Friendship Stargaze** in Oak Ridge, and special TAO events such as **Asteroid Occultations**, **Meteor Showers**, **Full Moonrises**, **Lunar (and other) Eclipses**, **Comet Watches**, and perhaps the occasional musical event.

These “Special Events” calendars for the current and subsequent months appear after the six-month “Public Fixed Events” calendar.

The facilities in the TAO buildings onsite will be open to the public during the “Public Fixed Events,” and will also usually be available when TAO is open to the public for some of the “Special Events.” **Please inquire regarding whether TAO will be open to the public for any “Special Event” you may wish to attend, since some may be restricted.** We will of course always try to accommodate enthusiastic visitors.

We recommend checking a TAO website such as **ORIONastronomy @ groups.io** before visiting, to confirm that listed events will proceed as planned; weather conditions for example may require a cancellation or change of date.

TAO Calendar Public Stargaze

Jan-Jun 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 04 Jan 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 18 Jan 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 01 Feb 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 15 Feb 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 01 Mar 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 15 Mar 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 05 Apr 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 19 Apr 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 03 May 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 17 May 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 07 Jun 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 21 Jun 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm

These 2025 TAO Public Stargaze events are scheduled for fixed calendar days during the weekend, which will hopefully prove convenient for many visitors with families, especially those bringing younger astronomers. Cancellations often take place in Winter and Spring, due to cold or icy conditions, or overcast and rainy skies.

TAO Calendar Public Stargaze

Jul-Dec 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 05 Jul 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Sat 19 Jul 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Sat 02 Aug 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Sat 16 Aug 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Sun 07 Sep 2025	<small>moved</small> ★	"1 st Sat" Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 20 Sep 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 04 Oct 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 18 Oct 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 01 Nov 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 15 Nov 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 06 Dec 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 20 Dec 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm

These 2025 TAO Public Stargaze events are scheduled for fixed calendar days during the weekend, which will hopefully prove convenient for many visitors with families, especially those bringing younger astronomers. Cancellations often take place in Winter, due to cold or icy conditions, or overcast and rainy skies.

TAO Calendar Special Events

Sep 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Ddd dd Sep 2025	★	International Friendship Stargaze (Oak Ridge)	8:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sun 07 Sep 2025	<small>moved</small> ★	“1st Sat” Public Stargaze also Moongaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sun 07 Sep 2025	○	Full Moon 02:09 pm Eastern		
Sat 20 Sep 2025	★	3 rd Sat Public Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Mon 21 Sep 2025	●	New Moon 03:54 pm Eastern		

TAOCalendar Special Events

Oct 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 04 Oct 2025		1 st Sat Public Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Tue 07 Oct 2025		Full Moon 11:47 am Eastern		
Sat 18 Oct 2025		3 rd Sat Public Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Tue 21 Oct 2025		New Moon 08:25 am Eastern		

Public Stargaze of Sat 16 Aug 2025

- Ted Barnes

The weather of Saturday 16 Aug 2025 appeared promising, and earlier in the week David Fields had encouraged ORION Board Members to attend this 3rd Saturday Public Stargaze, and to arrive at around 8 pm. The predicted weather was less than perfect, but appeared to be at least usable for a Public Stargaze. There would be no Moon (Moonset was 3:12 pm), so we might hope for a nice evening.

Unfortunately there were some personal complications. Don Spong was on travel, Art Allison had a conflict with a family event, Noah Frere was unavailable, and Kevin Wilson had recently moved to Ashville, so we had few ORION Board attendees. Another problem was that Rob Fowler had a car problem the day before and had been stranded in a local State Park until he could be rescued by David, about 1 am this morning.

The beautiful sunset of 8:16 pm Eastern, 16 Aug 2025.

Public Stargaze of Sat 16 Aug 2025 (cont.)

Additional TAO views at 8:16 pm Eastern, 16 Aug 2025, showing active weather to the North (above), and much more reassuring blue skies to the South (below).

Public Stargaze of Sat 16 Aug 2025 (cont.)

As a result of his traumatic car event, Rob decided to stay at home in the evening and recover. Due to these complications the usual morning public announcement confirming that there would be a Public Stargaze this evening was not distributed.

I was unaware of these developments, and appeared at the TAO gate about 7:54 pm with donuts and coffee and my camping chair; I thought that I might at least be able to catch a few late Perseids, and I had a talk prepared if needed. I found David in the TAO building, and he told me of the recent complications. Bob Edwards soon arrived; we were the full complement of ORION astronomers present for the evening. David encouraged me to download the latest issue of the Trapezium, which I had just finished the day before, and set that up on the projector for any potential visitors. However since the public had no notice confirming a Public Stargaze, we had no visitors at all until around 9 pm. At that time we were joined by two couples, Joan and Tom Koehn and Mark and Beth Vowell.

Our visitors and Bob Edwards, 9:50 pm Eastern, 16 Aug 2025.

Public Stargaze of Sat 16 Aug 2025 (cont.)

David and I gave presentations to our small but very knowledgeable group of visitors; I reviewed our recent observation of an occultation by asteroid 1776 Kuiper, and David summarized ORION and TAO activities.

After considerable discussion of the technical and economic aspects of amateur astronomy, and some deep questions that we could not answer at the time, we all proceeded outside where we showed our visitors some of the brighter constellations, as well as the Meade LX-200. Alas without Rob to operate it the Meade was not available for viewing, so we had to encourage our visitors to return again at a future date when we would have more staff present. Our visitors departed about 10 pm, as did Bob Edwards. David and I remained to discuss future prospects for local Astronomy until about 11 pm, when we departed. As is traditional, the sky improved considerably about that time.

David Fields describing the Meade LX-200 to out visitors,
9:50 pm Eastern, 16 Aug 2025.

Dark Stargaze of Monday 18 Aug 2025: Interstellar Object 3I/ATLAS

- Ted Barnes

The third known interstellar visitor to our solar system was discovered on 1 July 2025 by the excitingly named Asteroid Terrestrial-impact Last Alert System (ATLAS), and is known as 3I/ATLAS, or for the comet watchers, C/2025 N1. The two earlier interstellar visitors were the long and thin 1I/'Oumuamua of 2017 and the comet 2I/Borisov of 2019.

Mon 18 Aug 2025

Sunset	8:25 pm
Civ dusk	8:52 pm
Ast dusk	9:58 pm
Moonrise	1:43 am
Moonset	5:28 pm

Moon illum. 25%

**Waning Crescent Moon.
No Moon visible during this event.**

In view of the intense public interest in 3I/ATLAS, and the fact that it had increased in brightness from an early 18th magnitude to about 16.5, at our Orion Board Meeting on Monday 18 Aug 2025 I asked whether anyone might be interested in visiting TAO and attempting to image this fascinating new object. After we checked the weather forecast it became clear that the best opportunity that week would be that very Monday, and the forecast suggested that there might be only moderate cloud cover (like 20%) in the evening. The Tuesday forecast was less favorable, and the following days were discouraging. Unfortunately the current opportunity to capture 3I/ATLAS was closing. It was in Northern Scorpius, and as this was late Summer, this location was already crossing the Meridian about 8 pm Eastern. By early September it would no longer be easily visible, as it would pass closest to the Sun (1.36 AU minimum distance) on 29 Oct 2025, and by Nov 2025 would be a faint morning object. Closest approach to Earth would be a still distant 1.80 AU on 19 Dec 2025. A much closer encounter will involve Mars; 3I/ATLAS will pass only 0.19 AU from Mars on 3 Oct 2025. (A JPL Horizons orbit diagram is shown on the following page.)

So, given our local weather uncertainties, it appeared that our best opportunity to image 3I/ATLAS before it disappeared into the evening twilight might well be that night, Mon-Tue 18-19 Aug 2025.

Dark Stargaze of Monday 18 Aug 2025: 3I/ATLAS (cont.)

A JPL Horizons orbit diagram showing the position of 3I/ATLAS (a.k.a. C/2025 N1, white trajectory and text) and the inner solar system at UT 4:00 am 19 Aug 2025, the approximate time of the TAO images shown here. Earth distance is 2.663 AU.

Dark Stargaze of Monday 18 Aug 2025: 3I/ATLAS (cont.)

Those who decided they could attend this event and attempt to image 3I/ATLAS were Ted (moi), Richard Piety, David Fields and Rob Fowler. We agreed to meet at TAO about 8 pm. David and Rob planned to use the Meade LX-200, so there was some concern about how well they would be able to capture this object above the treeline.

On my arrival I decided to check the visibility from the two new concrete pads, North and Northeast. I thought Northeast might be more favorable for capturing 3I/ATLAS, as one would be able to see some distance West of the Meridian. It was clear that the treeline as seen from the Southeast pad was actually well above both domes, and there was considerable visibility from the Meridian to the West, so this position did appear to be the most favorable. So, I set up there. (See image below.) One pleasant surprise was that my tripod legs required no individual extensions, since the pad was quite flat.

My position on the Northeast pad, my first use of that location, at 8:04 pm. Note that the large dome only reaches about halfway to the top of the treeline.

Dark Stargaze of Monday 18 Aug 2025: 3I/ATLAS (cont.)

Richard arrived soon after 8 pm, and also began setting up on the Northeast pad. It was *very* hot and humid, with some insects, all of which slowed one's progress in assembling observing equipment, which nonetheless still required frequent rest stops. I was busy with that until about 9:10 pm, and was happy to find that my CGX mount's alignment platform didn't require much adjustment to reach Polaris.

I hadn't combined the ZWO ASI294MCP camera with the Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph for some time, and initially had much difficulty with focus and in finding my first alignment star, Kolchab. I then gradually added alignment stars to the East, specifically Pherkad, Schedar, Altair and Ascella. The SharpCap pulldown tool "Plate Solve and Resync" was working well, and was invaluable in these alignments. (Part of the problem was that the laser was poorly collimated, which often happens when I move the telescope. Eventually I recollimated the laser, which made life easier.) Then a new problem appeared, 3I/ATLAS was already well past the Meridian to the West, and I had a short camera USB3.0 cable, so I had to pull both the OTA and guiding camera cables out, move them to the other side of the mount and OTA, reconnect them, and hope for the best. I was lucky, both images promptly returned. I then had to slew all the way around the sky to the West side of the Meridian, where I added Antares and Dschubba as my last alignment stars. By then it was already about 10:30 pm, and I was happy to see that 3I/ATLAS was still relatively high in the sky; at 10:30 pm it was at $\text{Alt@Azi} = 26^\circ@223^\circ$, and at 11:00 pm it was still at $22^\circ@229^\circ$. About 10:40 pm I slewed to the 11:00 pm 3I/ATLAS coordinates. (I had earlier generated an Ephemeris using JPL Horizons.) SharpCap confirmed that I was in the right field by plate solving. The relevant portion of the sky near Scorpius, Ophiuchus and Libra at 11:00 pm, as well as 3I/ATLAS, generated using TheSkyX, is shown in the star chart on the next page.

Since my preparations had been somewhat hurried I hadn't prepared detailed fine-scale reference star charts, but the plate solve tool on SharpCap confirmed

Dark Stargaze of Monday 18 Aug 2025: 3I/ATLAS (cont.)

A large scale sky chart including 3I/ATLAS (red text and circle with crosshairs) near the center, generated using TheSkyX. This is the configuration of the sky at 11:00 pm Eastern, 18 Aug 2025; 3I/ATLAS was very close to the Scorpius-Libra border.

Dark Stargaze of Monday 18 Aug 2025: 3I/ATLAS (cont.)

that I was in the correct field for 3I/ATLAS. To capture 3I/ATLAS, initially at *ca.* 11:00 pm I tried stacking 4sG570 frames; these confirmed that I did have a faint asteroid-like object in about the expected position, but these frames were rather dark. From *ca.* 11:13 pm I switched to various stack lengths of 8sG570 frames, and from *ca.* 11:31 pm to 11:40 pm I captured shorter stacks of up to 37x15sG570 frames, almost 9 minutes. The most successful was a 16-min exposure of 120x8sG570 frames, which appears with post-processing on the second page following page and the issue cover. I added black arrows showing the predicted JPL Horizons path for Eastern time 9 pm 18 Aug to 2 am 19 Aug, with a one hour gap left open to display the trail of 3I/ATLAS.

I also attempted to capture a series of shorter 3-min stacks starting from 11:40 pm, but unfortunately the first two included bright star image glitches, and after the third I was in the treeline, and had to move to a new object. I encountered the top of the treeline at about 11:50 pm, location Alt@Azi = 14°@238°, and moved on to another field.

Meanwhile, regarding my colleagues:

Richard Piety arrived about 8:20 pm and began setting up next to me, on the East side of the Northeast pad. Richard used a Stellarvue SVT115 4-inch refractor on an ioptron mount, with an 0.8 field flattener / reducer, so the native $f7$, $f_L = 800$ mm performance of his telescope was reduced to $f5.6$, and f_L to 640 mm. His chosen field was 1920x1080 px, corresponding to a f.o.v. of 47'x26'. He used a ZWO ASI294MCP camera with 4.63 μm pixels, which gave a resolution of *ca.* 1.48 sec/px.

While setting up, Richard surprised me by asking if he could turn on a fan. (Outside?) Since it was so very warm and humid, with little breeze, I found that this fan was actually a great comfort.

Dark Stargaze of Monday 18 Aug 2025: 3I/ATLAS (cont.)

Richard proved to be rather quiet and even dismissive regarding his imaging progress, so it was only several days later when looking at some images he had sent me at my request that I found that he had captured a nice, sharp image of 3I/ATLAS relatively early in the evening! (See two pages following, and the Trapezium cover image.) This image was a 7x60s stack which I enlarged, cropped, and post-processed here. Richard quoted an exposure end time corresponding to a midpoint of 10:04:49 pm; the JPL Ephemeris for 10:05 pm corresponds accurately to the position of 3I/ATLAS in the image, with an error of about a 1 pixel scale.

An ASPS plate solve of his later image `Stack_1frames_240s` showed that 3I/ATLAS had then advanced to a midpoint position corresponding to *ca.* 10:25 pm Eastern (according to the JPL Horizons Ephemeris), with a fitted camera angle of -138.06° and a fitted focal length of $f_L = 647$ mm. A detailed calculation reveals that this camera angle is equivalent to the ASPS-fitted camera angle of 41.93° found for the earlier 10:05 pm image. :-) (Math joke.) Since 3I/ATLAS had now moved from its previous position, the underlying 17.5 g-mag star that had boosted its apparent brightness by about 0.4 magnitudes is visible in this later image (especially with additional post-processing). Richard later changed telescope configuration, but the resulting images showed significant star trailing, and were considered less successful; 3I/ATLAS could not be identified among the many brighter trailed stars.

David and Rob encountered some complications in using the Meade to image 3I/ATLAS. First, Rob was delayed until about 9:30 pm, so their observing time was limited. Second, they were much closer to the trees to the South, so they had an imaging cutoff time earlier in the evening, about 11 pm. Third, they encountered an especially aggressive pair of surprisingly large bees at some stage. I could only hear the results of this encounter from a distance through the darkness, but they were apparently quite a distraction. Rob did manage to capture a star field which he hoped contained 3I/ATLAS, as shown on the following page. My ASPS plate solver program initially could not identify this mystery field.

Dark Stargaze of Monday 18 Aug 2025: 3I/ATLAS (cont.)

This image shows a 10.4' sq. region in Scorpius and Libra, with JPL Horizons' predicted path of 3I/ATLAS (black arrows) for the Eastern time periods 9-11 pm 18 Aug and 12-2 am 19 Aug. The trail is from a 16-min stack of 120x8sG570 frames, 11:14 - 11:30 pm, which interpolates nicely between the two predicted path sections. The end of the trail image in J2000.0 coordinates is *ca.* RA 16 02 09.5, Dec -15 53 52. Camera angle = -115.5°.

Dark Stargaze of Monday 18 Aug 2025: 3I/ATLAS (cont.)

This raw png stack of 7 frames, each 60s, showing the field of 3I/ATLAS, was captured by Richard Piety at midpoint time 10:04:49 pm Eastern, 18 Aug 2025. An ASPS plate solve finds field center J2000.0 coordinates of RA 16 02 25, Dec -15 52 56, camera angle = 41.9°.

A crop from an ASPS plate solve, showing a small region near the center of the field above. The circled “extra” star is at J2000.0 coordinates RA 16 02 19.0, Dec -15 54 14. The JPL Horizons value for the position of 3I/ATLAS at 10:05 pm is RA 16 02 18.9, Dec -15 54 15, which agrees with the position of the circled object to about 1 pixel accuracy. The (Gaia) g-mags of many comparison stars are also shown. 3I/ATLAS appears brighter than the predicted 16.5; an accidentally line-of-sight g-mag 17.5 star implies an apparent combined g-mag of 16.1.

Dark Stargaze of Monday 18 Aug 2025: 3I/ATLAS (cont.)

This is the “last chance” star field captured about 11 pm by Rob and David on the Meade LX-200, using a ZWO ASI294MCP. They had hoped to recognize this as the field of 3I/ATLAS, but that has encountered some ambiguities. With this telescope and camera, full field is about 22’x15’. This image has been subject to post-processing, mainly for intensity and contrast. And it’s a dandy shade of purple. Identification of this “mystery field” is discussed on the following page.

Dark Stargaze of Monday 18 Aug 2025: 3I/ATLAS (cont.)

Identification of the Meade LX-200 starfield shown on the previous page, provided by Rob Fowler, proved to be a challenge. I initially converted the png to a jpg so it could run on my ASPS plate solver program, and used a focal length of 3048 mm (Meade LX-200) and a pixel size of $4.63\ \mu\text{m}$ (ASI294MCP camera), but ASPS repeatedly failed to solve. A visual inspection also failed, although the line of three stars on the right border just above the lower right corner appeared very similar to three stars in the two other groups' large field images. The brightest star, middle of the three, might well be the g-mag 10.4 star BD-15 4234, at RA 16 02 10.3, Dec -15 51 01. (It was.)

Rob advised me that the scale of the image might be a problem, since he had used his DaVinci program to resize it by about a factor of two after stacking using SharpCap. Rob attempted to restore the image to the something close to its original scale. I plate solved that resized image in ASPS, which reported a solution (*albeit* with $f_L = 3019\ \text{mm}$), but the solved image still had some kind of problem with the star coordinates. I eventually realized that the image was also parity-inverted. Solving a horizontal-parity-flipped copy in ASPS then gave a plate-solved image with stars at the correct coordinates.

Once I was in business with sensible star coordinates, I inspected the field where the JPL Ephemeris indicated that 3I/ATLAS should reside just after 11 pm. I soon identified an “extra” object along the predicted trajectory of 3I/ATLAS of about the right magnitude, at ASPS coordinates RA 16 02 12.3, Dec -15 54 06. JPL anticipated that 3I/ATLAS would be at RA 16 02 12.34, -15 53 59.2 at 11:04 pm, a fair if not perfect match. (A discrepancy of $7''$ in Dec was also noted in nearby stars, and the 3I “blob” itself is about $7''$ in width.) It appeared that we had found 3I/ATLAS in the Meade image!

3I/ATLAS, in the inverted -parity image.

TAO Dark Stargaze of Monday 18 Aug 2025: 3I/ATLAS (cont.)

One outstanding question was the precise time at which this Meade image was captured. As noted above, the JPL Ephemeris implied that 3I/ATLAS was at essentially the same coordinates as the “blob” at 11:04 pm, so I needed to confirm that this was close to the midpoint time actually recorded for this stack. Rob checked the SharpCap image log, and found that the start, midpoint and end capture times were respectively 11:08:36 pm, 11:09:27 pm, and 11:10:18 pm. So, the actual recorded capture midpoint was about 5 minutes AFTER the time suggested by the JPL Ephemeris from the “blob’s” coordinates in the image. Is this 5 minute time difference a problem?

Probably not. During the 5 minute period from 11:04 pm to 11:09 pm the position of 3I/ATLAS should change by $\Delta\text{RA} = -0.55\text{s}$ and $\Delta\text{Dec} = +1.3''$, corresponding to an angle of about 8 asecs (about 0.2 pink circle diameters in the small image on the previous page, about the width of the putative 3I “blob” itself). Of course one would prefer to have precise agreement between the inferred and recorded image times, but in view of the limited position accuracy determination possible here, this 5 minute time difference appears to be of just marginal significance.

In summary, our attempt to image the 3rd identified interstellar object “3I/ATLAS” at TAO on 18-19 Aug 2025 was clearly a success. We fielded three independent setups, Richard Piety’s Stellarvue refractor, Ted Barnes’s Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph, and David Fields and Rob Fowler with TAO’s Meade LX-200. Each group generated at least one image of 3I/ATLAS, and all are represented on the cover page. Of course there were difficulties; Richard and Ted were both setting up at a new location, and in their fixed location Rob and David had problems with a low treeline and woke insects. And there were some equipment complications, as always, but everyone now has ideas regarding how their results can be improved at the next such event. Bring on the interstellar visitors, we are ready for them! (See page three.)

TAO Dark Stargaze of Saturday 30 Aug 2025:

- Ted Barnes

The original concept of a Dark Stargaze was that this would be an event for our more dedicated astronomers, when conditions were expected to be especially favorable for observing, astrophotography and related dark sky activities. Since when this might happen was dependent on the usually uncertain weather conditions, a discussion over the preceding few days would usually determine when a Dark Stargaze actually took place. The most recent was Monday 18 August, when the (successful) possibility of imaging the interstellar object 3I/ATLAS brought out several ORION astronomers.

Recently I have been monitoring the 10-day weather forecast on weather dot com, to try to anticipate favorable dates for future Dark Stargazes. As of 29 Aug the favorable possibilities were Sat 30 Aug (also a weekend, and including a very late 4:22 am Eastern, 31 Aug asteroid occultation), the block of 4-7 Sep, and at the end of the forecast period, 11-12 Sep. The Sep dates unfortunately include bright moonlight, with a Full Moon on 7 Sep. I had mentioned Sat 30 Aug a few days in advance, and several potential observers confirmed that they would be interested, mainly through online discussions using WhatsApp, our usual planning tool. However nothing was officially approved by David, who had been busy with the Oak Ridge Peace Bell Stargaze on Thu 28 Aug, and said that he preferred to address events sequentially, as they required some preparation time.

When the online discussion continued on the morning of 30 Aug, David stated that he would not be opening TAO that day. That's the end of that, I thought, and advised the other astronomers of David's decision. I turned off my cell

Sat 30 Aug 2025

Sunset	8:09 pm
Civ dusk	8:35 pm
Ast dusk	9:39 pm
Moonrise	2:18 pm
Moonset	11:52 pm

Moon illum. 45%

Waxing Crescent Moon.
Moon visible until midnight.

TAO Dark Stargaze of Saturday 30 Aug 2025: (cont.)

phone and went on with other weekend activities. Oh well. I had thought the night would likely involve “telescope practice,” like alignment and camera format experiments, so perhaps I wouldn’t miss much. That 4:22 am occultation was too late for serious consideration anyway, and I was admittedly rather tired from a new MD-imposed low calorie diet, which is intended to address a serious medical problem.

Sometime around 3 pm I switched on my cell phone again, and found that the discussion of a Dark Stargaze had continued and evolved. Now David was planning to be there, and encouraged me to show up with moon music! I replied that I had given up plans for a 30 Aug Dark Stargaze when he said he would not be opening up TAO. Perhaps I had misunderstood? David replied that one should never give up. Rob chimed in and said he had been silent in this discussion because he didn’t want to stay up until 5 am (which was not actually expected of anyone, another miscommunication alas), but he would likely be there until midnight. Noah said he would not attend, but perhaps he was an exception.

Clearly I don’t understand people. I had thought this TAO event was declined by David, but after some additional consideration it appeared that it might be a “go” after all. I was tempted, but I really was tired from my diet, and packing my van for a trip to TAO usually requires a few hours of preparation, so I decided to continue a restful Saturday at home. I was asleep by 8 pm. Now it is early morning on Sun 31 Aug, and I am wondering whether the Dark Stargaze actually took place. Most mysterious. Perhaps there would be some images of the event, and some lovely new astrophotography?

A check of my cell phone reveals that the 30 Aug Dark Stargaze DID take place; David had messaged me at 12:32 am 31 Aug to say that Rob was ill, but he and Don Spong, Art Allison and Richard Piety (and Sunny) were there. So, I am looking forward to seeing any new images from this Dark Stargaze!

TAO Dark Stargaze of Saturday 30 Aug 2025: (cont.)

NGC7293, the Helix Nebula in Aquarius.

A stack of 10x30sec frames at auto gain, max 285.

Captured by Richard Piety at TAO.

Equipment as described in the preceding 3I/ATLAS article.

A Night of Lunacy. Public & Dark Moongaze of Sunday 07 Sep 2025 :

- Ted Barnes

Although the 1st Saturday Public Stargaze should have been on 06 Sep 2025, the weather was overcast with thunderstorms, so we decided to postpone it until Sunday, which was predicted to have clear skies and a near perfect sky quality in the Clear Sky Chart. Just to confuse the issue there was also a Full Moon, nominally at 2:09 pm, so we would have an excellent sky combined with a Full Moon. At least we could celebrate the

Moonrise, officially at 8:01 pm at our location. And for those interested in asteroid occultations, TWO were on offer that evening, by asteroids 165 Loreley at 9:50:40 pm and 1094 Siberia at 12:47:48 am the next morning. Alas both stars are quite faint at 14th mag, so the Full Moon will make recording either event a true challenge. Nonetheless, since we and Don Spong also expressed interest in attempting astrophotography that evening, this was also considered a Dark Stargaze night.

In honor of the Full Moon, Don brought his trumpet, and performed selections of Moon-related music as the Moon rose higher in the East, his first selection being “Moonmen.”

Sun 07 Sep 2025

Sunset	7:58 pm
Civ dusk	8:24 pm
Ast dusk	9:26 pm
Moonrise	8:01 pm
Moonset*	8:09 am
	*08 Sep

Moon illum. 100%

Full Moon

Full Moon during this event.

8:30 pm. Full Moon rising in Druidic fashion.

Don Spong encourages the Moon to continue rising.

A Night of Lunacy. (cont.)

In the Sector of the Domes, one can see Rob Fowler, Art Allison and David Fields setting up the Meade LX-200 and preparing to welcome visitors. Sonny the Astrodog was not impressed by the paucity of ham and cheese rolls at this event.

As part of the Lunar welcoming activities, I started my traditional set of 20 pieces of Moon Music on the NE pad, beginning with Debussy's *Claire de Lune* and ending with four covers of *Blue Moon*, one actually being the original by The Marceles, care of Doo Wop Classics. The midpoint (item no.10) was "Werewolves of London" by Warren Zevon, which brought forth a few howls of recognition from across TAO. Larry Davidson wondered why I hadn't included *Moon River* in my moon music collection. Our original "poster" from the first 31 Oct 2023 "Moongaze" follows.

TAO 31 Oct 2023 "Halloween Night Moongaze"

Musical Program Begins at Moonrise, 7:14 pm Eastern

Debussy: Clair de Lune

Beethoven: Piano Sonata No.14 in C#-min, Op.27, No.2 "Moonlight"

The Doors: Hour For Magic

Liszt: Mephisto Waltz No.1, S.514

Credence Clearwater Revival: Bad Moon Rising

Cat Stevens: Moonshadow

Donovan: Season of the Witch

Warren Devon: Werewolves of London

Diana Kraal: Fly Me To The Moon

Van Morrison: Moondance

It's a Beautiful Day: Galileo

It's a Beautiful Day: Do You Remember the Sun

Fleetwood Mac: Sentimental Lady

Billie Holiday: Moonglow

Billie Holiday: What a Little Moonlight Can Do

Ella Fitzgerald: Moonlight Becomes You

CakeDrop: Gimme That Moonlight

Frank Sinatra: It's Only a Paper Moon

Glenn Miller: Moonlight Serenade

Glenn Miller: Blue Moon (1939)

Frank Sinatra: Blue Moon

Elvis Presley: Blue Moon

The Marceles: Blue Moon (1961)

From our first TAO Moongaze, 31 Oct 2023.

A Night of Lunacy. (cont.)

Presumably because this Public Stargaze event was on an unusual night (Sunday rather than Saturday), we had relatively few public visitors; something like 6 was estimated. However they were enthusiastic, and clearly enjoyed the Moonrise spirit. We gave three short astronomy talks for their benefit, these being a welcome by David Fields, an astrophotography talk by Don Spong, and a talk by your humble narrator about our recent threefold successful imaging at TAO on 18 Aug of the new interstellar object 3I/ATLAS. The talks were enthusiastically received, especially the image by Don Spong of the bright type Ia supernova in NGC7331, captured using his new and enormously expensive ZWO ASI2600 camera. (See the Astrophotography section in this issue.)

For the remainder of the evening I was primarily occupied with preparing to capture an occultation. One occasionally forgets to bring important equipment on an astrophotography outing, because there are so many relatively minor important components, cables, power supplies, weights, lens caps, cameras and so forth. In this case I had made a MAJOR omission, and had forgotten my camera's little gps antenna. To precisely time an occultation one needs a special camera with a gps capability, and at present there is only one suitable model, the QHYCCD QHY174M-GPS camera. Alas without the gps antenna it could not receive gps satellite data, so accurate timing, which is an essential part of observing an asteroid occultation, would be impossible. Repeated searches confirmed that I really had failed to pack my gps antenna. Spoiled my whole evening.

So, I instead simply went through the usual telescope setup procedures, meaning alignment on a set of *ca.* 10 bright stars, doing practice slews between them, and gradually moving the telescope's pointing direction towards the location of the night's final occultation, with the asteroid 1094 Siberia, in Sagittarius. Somewhere along the way Richard felt sorry for me, and since he had already attempted to record the occultation with 165 Loreley at 9:50 pm, he loaned me his gps antenna so I could attempt the later occultation. I connected his gps to my camera, and it quickly locked on satellites and began showing time and location data. I was in business!

A Night of Lunacy. (cont.)

The days of 06-07 Sep 2025 had also been full of Occultation information, since the annual IOTA conference had taken place as a public zoom meeting during that period, from *ca.* 4-8 pm Eastern daily. New attendees included Rob Fowler, Richard Piety (in the images), and myself (selfie in the images). I won't go into details, but it was certainly interesting to see that the leading occultation astronomers looked very much like I expected. (See below.) It was also interesting to hear about topics such as the risks to life and limb encountered by occultation observers in the desert Southwest. (See the following page.) The talks were fascinating; unfortunately I had to leave midway through the second day in order to arrive at the TAO Moongaze reasonably early.

Early arrivals for the IOTA Annual Occultations Online Meeting, 06 Sep 2025.

A Night of Lunacy. (cont.)

A veteran IOTA Speaker (David Dunham?) reviews some of the challenges encountered by mobile occultation observers in the desert Southwest.

After hearing about the difficulties encountered by others in the IOTA corps of observers, setting up to observe occultations at TAO that very night seemed much less challenging. Our principal night hazards were bright moonlight, moon music, skeptical talk attendees, atrocious puns from our colleagues, and forgotten equipment (*mea culpa*). And perhaps screech owls, coyotes, spiders, and feather-based alien life forms. Admittedly, our lists of hazards do include some of the same concerns.

A Night of Lunacy. (cont.)

So, returning to our TAO occultation experiences; since I had forgotten my gps antenna I was initially SOL, so Richard attempted the first occultation himself, involving the asteroid 165 Loreley at midpoint 9:50:47 pm. I had not looked at the details; this proved to be a rather challenging event. First, the target star UCAC4 319-127673 was at g-mag 13.9, fainter than any I had ever recorded in an occultation; second, the asteroid itself at mag 13.0 was over twice as bright as the target star, so one would only see a decrease in brightness by 0.4 magnitudes, from the combined 12.6 (13.0 & 13.9) to the asteroid alone (13.0). This would be a reduction of brightness of the combined 12.6 mag source by only 30%, perhaps difficult to observe. In some compensation this would be a long event, a duration of 15.6 secs was predicted. (165 Loreley is an Outer Main Belt asteroid, with a rather large diameter of *ca.* 180 km.) Richard set his QHY174M-GPS camera to a gain of 400 and a frame exposure of 500 ms, with a reduced ROI of 1280x1024, and recorded a SER movie through the predicted event time. By running this SER movie file through Pymovie and Pyote, Richard extracted a light curve showing an occultation with about the expected time and duration (see below).

Richard's 165 Loreley lightcurve, showing a Pyote square-well fit that gives an occultation duration of 15.0 \pm 1.6 secs and a midpoint of 9:50:36 pm Eastern.

A Night of Lunacy. (cont.)

Richard's fitted midpoint time is consistent with the predicted event midpoint time of 9:50:37 pm Eastern, which had an estimated error of 1 sec. This was his second successful occultation observation, this time with a seriously faint target star! Previously, 22 Mar 2025, he had observed an occultation involving the much brighter 11.0 mag asteroid 14 Irene, from Norris Lake State Park.

The second occultation of the night involved the (inner Middle) Main Belt asteroid 1094 Siberia, much smaller at 18 km diameter. This event was predicted to be at midpoint 12:47:48 am Eastern on 08 Sep 2025, with a maximum duration of 3.0 seconds. With help from SharpCap's plate solver, after some alignment bungling, I found the field in question, at J2000.0 coordinates RA 19 08 32.9 and Dec -14 43 45 in Sagittarius, near Scutum and Aquila. The target star was a faint g-mag 13.5, with a nearby brighter companion of g-mag 12.0. The asteroid itself, at mag 16.6, was not expected to be visible in my 500 ms frames. I captured a SER movie of 200 frames starting just after 12:47:00 am, with an ROI of 1024x768, and later extracted separate jpg frames from the SER file for inspection. I had misidentified the target and companion star with a nearby brighter pair, which alas convinced me that I could significantly reduce the camera gain: I accordingly set it to a low gain of 344 (480 is max). As the actual (nearby) pair was much fainter, the raw frames were quite dark, and had to be post processed for brightness and contrast. I also had trouble with image position stability; PHD2 guidance suffered instabilities and had to be turned off, which resulted in occasional unguided image drift. This also happened close to the event time, so using Pymovie and Pyote (which require a reasonably stable image) was not feasible. I instead had to extract and compare individual frames. I also encountered atmospheric turbulence, so the faint target star was occasionally blurred. Of the 200 frames, I concluded that the target star disappeared just before frame 91 and reappeared just before frame 98, so the duration was 3.4 \pm 0.4 secs (using a half frame width as my \pm time error estimate), and the midpoint time was 12:47:47.2(2) am Eastern, both consistent with the predictions in Occult Watcher. Although there had been serious complications, this was a successful and enjoyable night of lunacy for all concerned.

A Night of Lunacy. (cont.)

The occultation by 1094 Siberia: Bracketing frames **90** and **98** and the midpoint frame **94** (all post processed) are shown below.

A Night of Lunacy. (cont.)

Boö

UMa

laser

Cas

And

Peg

A retrospective panoramic view from the glow dome, courtesy Rob Fowler.

The evening Sky Map for September 2025 from skymaps.com.

The Evening Sky Map

FREE* EACH MONTH FOR YOU TO EXPLORE, LEARN & ENJOY THE NIGHT SKY

Sky Calendar – September 2025

Follow us on Bluesky
skymaps.com/bsky/

- 7 **Total Lunar Eclipse** begins at 17:31 UT and ends at 18:53 UT. Greatest eclipse at 18:12 UT. Partial phases begin at 16:27 UT and end at 19:56 UT. During totality the Moon will appear red-orange in color (the Earth's shadow). This eclipse favors skywatchers in Europe, Africa, Asia and Australia.
 - 7 **Full Moon** at 18:09 UT.
 - 8 **Moon near Saturn** at 18h UT (morning sky). Mag. 0.6.
 - 10 **Moon at perigee** (closest to Earth) at 12:14 UT (distance 364,777km; angular size 32.8').
 - 12 **Moon near the Pleiades** at 23h UT (morning sky).
 - 13 **Mars 2.2° NNE of Spica** at 17h UT (33° from Sun, evening sky). Mags. 1.6 and 1.0.
 - 14 **Last Quarter Moon** at 10:34 UT.
 - 16 **Moon near Jupiter** at 13h UT (morning sky). Mag. -2.1.
 - 19 **Moon, Venus & Regulus** within 1.2° circle at 13h UT (27° from Sun, morning sky). Mags. -3.9 and 1.4.
 - 21 **Saturn at opposition** (opposite the Sun) at 6h UT. The planet is at its closest and brightest. Mag. 0.6.
 - 21 **Partial Solar Eclipse** at 19:42 UT (greatest eclipse). Visible from the South Pacific, New Zealand and Antarctica. Begins 17:30 UT. Ends 21:54 UT.
 - 21 **New Moon** at 19:53 UT. Start of lunation 1271.
 - 22 **September equinox** at 18:19 UT. The time when the Sun reaches the point along the ecliptic where it crosses into the southern celestial hemisphere marking the start of autumn in the Northern Hemisphere and spring in the Southern Hemisphere.
 - 23 **Neptune at opposition** at 13h UT. Mag. 7.8.
 - 23 **Moon near Spica** at 22h UT (evening sky).
 - 24 **Moon near Mars** at 12h UT (evening sky). Mag. 1.6.
 - 26 **Moon at apogee** (farthest from Earth) at 10h UT (distance 405,548km; angular size 29.5').
 - 27 **Moon near Antares** at 16h UT (evening sky). Occultation visible from Antarctica and north-western French Southern Territories.
 - 29 **First Quarter Moon** at 23:54 UT.
- More sky events and links at <http://Skymaps.com/skycalendar/>**
All times in Universal Time (UT). (USA Eastern Summer Time = UT - 4 hours.)

Support The Evening Sky Map

- Helping curious minds to explore the night sky since January 2000 •
- Recommended Products for Sky Watchers:** skymaps.com/store/
- All sales support the continued production of this free resource

NORTHERN HEMISPHERE SEPTEMBER 2025

SKY MAP SHOWS HOW THE NIGHT SKY LOOKS

EARLY SEPT 9 PM

LATE SEPT 8 PM

Map 1 shows the twilight starting sky map drawn for a latitude of 40° north and is suitable for latitudes up to 15° north or south of this

- Symbols**
- Galaxy
 - Double Star
 - Variable Star
 - Diffuse Nebula
 - Planetary Nebula
 - Open Star Cluster
 - Globular Star Cluster

Star Magnitudes ● ● ● ● ●
-1 0 1 2 3 4

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* TERMS OF USE: FREE FOR NON-COMMERCIAL EDUCATIONAL USE. ASTRONOMY EDUCATION GROUPS MAY FREELY DISTRIBUTE PRINTED HANDBOOKS. FULL DETAILS AT <http://skymaps.com/terms.html>

Note: a nice interactive sky chart from Sky and Telescope may be found at the link <https://skyandtelescope.org/interactive-sky-chart/>

Astrophotography

Type Ia Supernova SN2025rbs

- Don Spong

The first image below is my try at capturing a recent Type Ia supernova, SN2025rbs. This supernova was first discovered on July 14, 2025 by the Gravitational-wave Optical Transient Observatory (GOTO), and is now the brightest supernova visible from Earth. As indicated below, it is the small bright dot just to the left of the galactic center of NGC 7331, which is about 50 million ly from Earth, in the northern constellation Pegasus. The supernova is thought to have been caused by a thermonuclear detonation of a white dwarf as it accreted material from a nearby companion in a binary star system. Since this galaxy was small (apparent size 10.5'×3.7'), I had to go to the native 2000mm focal length on my Celestron 8" Edge HD to get the maximum magnification. NGC 7331 was discovered by William Herschel on 6 September 1784, and is often called the Milky Way's twin since it is similar in size and structure to the Milky Way. This image was taken at Tamke-Allen Observatory on the evening of September 30, 2025 and is based on stacking ten 2-minute exposures. For both this and the next image, I used a ZWO AM5 mount, an ORION 240mm focal length guide scope with a ZWO ASI 220 monochrome guide camera, and everything was controlled by an ASI AIR computer. The main camera is a ZWO ASI 2600MC, and an Antlia Tri-band filter was used. (An enlarged version of this image is shown on the page following. - Ed.)

Type Ia supernova SN2025rbs in the spiral galaxy NGC 3771, in Pegasus.

The glorious Trifid Nebula

- Don Spong

The following image is the Trifid Nebula, Messier 20. This was also done on the evening of Aug. 30, 2025, at TAO. Although I have imaged M20 previously, I wanted to try it again using my new ZWO ASI 2600MC camera, with the Celestron's native 2000mm focal length. Its size was a good fit for this focal length, and the delicate color variations were a good test for the new camera, which is my first camera with a 16-bit dynamic range. This image was made by stacking eleven 2-minute exposures.

A Patch of Scorpius

- Ted Barnes

About midnight on the Dark Stargaze of 18-19 Aug, after my imaging of 3I/ATLAS was stopped by the arrival of the treeline, since it was still relatively early on a clear night I used CPWI to slew to something called the Butterfly Nebula. Somewhere I made a mistake, and instead arrived at a different rich field somewhere in Scorpius. As long as I was there I captured several images using my ASI294MCP camera, including this 23x8sG570 stack, a 4144x2822 full field, f.o.v. 40'x27'. A plate solve tells me the J2000.0 coordinates are RA 17 25 41, Dec -31 08 57. This field is just below Ophiuchus, and includes star clouds not far from the galactic center. The “comma” asterism of four stars at middle upper left (g-mags 9.6 through 12.9) appears correlated, but from top their Gaia distances are respectively 1.00, 1.09, 0.39 and 0.40 kpc with *ca.* 1-2% errors, so their apparent remarkable alignment is actually line-of-sight, at least in part. Below and right of this asterism is a long band of dust that partly obscures the star cloud visible near the middle. The brightest stars in this image are about g-magnitude 9.5. The ASPS plate solver fitted camera angle is 64.84°, with N about 25° below left.

Appendices

Astronomy

- tb

Some numbers are quoted to several-digit accuracy where appropriate.
Exact numerical relationships are indicated as such.

1 ly = 1 ly (Julian) = *exactly* 9 460 730 472 580. 8 km = 63 241. 077 084 ... AU
c = speed of light = *exactly* 299 792 458 m/s = *exactly* ☺ 1 ly/yr.
1 AU = *exactly* 149 597 870. 7 km
1 parsec (pc) = 3. 261 598 ... light years (ly)
1 yr (Julian) = *exactly* 365.25 d = *exactly* 31 557 600 s
1 d = *exactly* 86 400 s

distance to α Cen A = 1.346(2) pc = 4.390(8) ly
distance to the center of the galaxy ~ 8 kpc ~ 25 kly (considerable uncertainty)

1 nm = 1 nanometer = 10^{-9} m *exactly*
 H_{α} wavelength = 656.2 nm

+ 0.5 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{1/5}$ x fainter =	1. 584 893 ... x fainter
+ 1 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{2/5}$ x fainter =	2. 511 886 ... x fainter
+ 2 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{4/5}$ x fainter =	6. 309 ... x fainter
+ 2.5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^1 x fainter =	10 x fainter
+ 3 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{6/5}$ x fainter =	15. 848 ... x fainter
+ 4 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{8/5}$ x fainter =	39. 810 ... x fainter
+ 5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^2 x fainter =	100 x fainter
+ 6 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{12/5}$ x fainter =	251. 188 ... x fainter
+ 7.5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^3 x fainter =	1000 x fainter
+ 8 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{16/5}$ x fainter =	1584. 893 ... x fainter
+ 10 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^4 x fainter =	10 000 x fainter
+ 20 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^8 x fainter =	100 000 000 x fainter

Brightness is proportional to $1 / \text{distance}^2$

10 x more distant = *exactly* 10^2 x fainter = + 5 change in magnitude
 10^2 x more distant = *exactly* 10^4 x fainter = + 10 change in mag
 10^3 x more distant = *exactly* 10^6 x fainter = + 15 change in mag

Absolute magnitude M_{abs} is the brightness as seen from a distance of 10 pc.
 M_{abs} (our sun) = 4.83

17th mag is about 1 optical photon / cm^2 s (Barnes's rule ☺).

Astronomy (cont.)

Some numbers are quoted to several-digit accuracy where appropriate. *Exact* numerical relationships are indicated as such.

R.A. = RA = Right Ascension = the angle ϕ around the celestial polar axis, usually quoted in hours, minutes, and seconds (*h m s*); analogous to longitude.

Dec = Declination = the angle θ above the celestial equator, usually quoted in degrees, minutes, and seconds ($^{\circ} \ ' \ ''$); analogous to latitude.

The RA (ϕ) and Dec (θ) angles, together with a reference epoch such as J2000.0, specify an object's direction in the sky.

A unit length vector ("unit vector") η pointing towards an object in the sky ("on the celestial sphere") in terms of RA (ϕ) and Dec (θ) angles is given by

$$\eta = \cos(\theta) \cos(\phi) \mathbf{x} + \cos(\theta) \sin(\phi) \mathbf{y} + \sin(\theta) \mathbf{z} = C (c \mathbf{x} + s \mathbf{y}) + S \mathbf{z}$$

The arc angle Θ_{12} between any two directions in the sky η_1 and η_2 (or any two stars) using the dot product formula and some obvious abbreviations, satisfies

$$\cos(\Theta_{12}) = \sin(\theta_1)\sin(\theta_2) + \cos(\theta_1)\cos(\theta_2)\cos(\phi_1 - \phi_2) = S_1 S_2 + C_1 C_2 c_{1-2}$$

$$1 \text{ degree} = \pi/180 \text{ radians} = 1.745 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ arcmin} = \pi/10800 \text{ radians} = 2.909 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ arcsec} = 1 \text{ asec} = \pi/648000 \text{ radians} = 4.848 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ mas} = 10^{-3} \text{ asec} = 4.848 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ asec @ 1 km} = 4.848 \text{ mm}$$

$$1 \text{ asec @ 1 AU} = 725.3 \text{ km}$$

$$1 \text{ asec @ 1 pc} = 1.0000 \text{ AU}$$

$$1 \text{ mas @ 1 kpc} = 1.0000 \text{ AU}$$

$$\text{Image resolution [asec/px]} = 206.3 * \text{pixel size}[\mu\text{m}] / \text{focal length [mm]}$$

JD = Julian Date (Astronomer's calendar) = a simple count of days starting at noon UT on Monday 1 Jan 4713 BC. That date and time was the start of Julian Day 0. The current JD can be inferred from the value on the cover of the Trapezium.

The 80 Brightest Stars

The 80 brightest stars (c/o Wikipedia), and their distances from Earth in light years, with errors (from Gaia data, or Simbad if needed as an alternative).

1	Sirius	8.709	0.0054	41	Menkalinan	81.1	0.46
2	Canopus	309.	16.	42	Atria	390.6	7.0
3	alpha Centauri A	4.395	0.0083	43	Alhena	109.3	8.2
4	Arcturus	36.72	0.22	44	Peacock	178.8	5.1
5	Vega	25.04	0.069	45	Alsephina	80.6	0.78
6	Capella	42.81	0.26	46	Mirzam	492.7	16.4
7	Rigel	863.	78.	47	Polaris	432.6	6.3
8	Procyon	11.46	0.051	48	Alphard	180.3	1.8
9	Archenar	139.4	3.4	49	Hamal	65.8	0.33
10	Betelgeuse	498.	63.	50	Diphda	96.3	0.46
11	beta Centauri	392.	24.	51	Mizar	81.1	0.93
12	Altair	16.73	0.049	52	Nunki	227.8	4.6
13	alpha Crucis	322.	16.	53	Menkent	58.8	0.21
14	Aldebaran	66.64	1.05	54	Alpheratz	97.0	1.01
15	Antares	554.	94.	55	Mirach	197.4	6.7
16	Spica	250.	13.	56	Rasalhague	48.6	0.77
17	Pollux	33.78	0.09	57	Algieba	130.1	2.7
18	Fomalhaut	25.13	0.09	58	Kochab	130.9	0.63
19	Deneb	1410	200	59	Saiph	974.	37.
20	Mimosa	279.	23.	60	Denebola	35.9	0.21
21	Regulus	79.30	0.67	61	Algol	89.9	3.47
22	Adhara	405.	7.0	62	Tiaki	177.0	4.0
23	Castor	50.68	0.032	63	Muhlifain	130.2	1.5
24	Shaula	571.2	7.5	64	Aspidiske	765.6	18.0
25	Gacrux	88.56	0.43	65	Suhail	544.5	10.0
26	Bellatrix	252.4	10.2	66	Alphecca	77.2	1.79
27	Elnath	133.9	1.9	67	Mintaka	692.5	85.
28	Miaplacidus	113.2	0.43	68	Sadr	1830	270
29	Alnilam	1980	540	69	Eltanin	154.3	0.7
30	Regor	1120	110	70	Schedar	231.5	8.2
31	Alnair	101.0	0.66	71	Naos	1080	40
32	Alnitak	736.	106.	72	Almach	393.0	49.
33	Alioth	82.55	0.42	73	Caph	54.7	0.35
34	Dubhe	122.9	2.2	74	Izar	235.9	8.4
35	Mirfak	506.	13.	75	alpha Lupi	464.6	11.
36	Wezen	1610	300	76	epsilon Centauri	427.5	27.
37	Sargas	300.	41.	77	Dschubba	491.2	66.
38	Kaus Australis	143.3	1.5	78	Larawag	63.7	0.27
39	Avior	605.	47.	79	eta Centauri	305.7	6.0
40	Alkaid	103.9	0.79	80	Merak	84.5	2.5

Notable Star-Pair Angles

Notable star pairs (from the set of the 80 brightest stars listed above) that are close to a multiple of 5° separation. The angles are in degrees.

		<u>Θ</u>	<u>Δθ</u>	<u>defect (%)</u>
Schedar	Caph	5	-0.085	1.7
Betelgeuse	Alnitak	10	0.017	0.17
Capella	Castor	30	-0.023	0.077
Procyon	Mirzam	30	-0.094	0.31
Elnath	Alnilam	30	-0.096	0.32
Alpheratz	Caph	30	0.060	0.20
Aldebaran	Pollux	45	0.013	0.029
Betelgeuse	Algol	50	-0.033	0.066
Alnitak	Naos	50	-0.049	0.098
Pollux	Alioth	60	0.065	0.11
Gacrux	Alphard	60	-0.001	0.002
Regulus	Bellatrix	70	-0.030	0.043
Sirius	Mirfak	80	-0.094	0.12
alpha_Centauri	Regulus	90	0.057	0.063
Vega	Denebola	90	-0.065	0.072
Fomalhaut	Caph	90	0.006	0.007
Deneb	Alnilam	120	0.059	0.049
Menkent	Mintaka	120	0.000	0.000
Sirius	Alphecca	135	-0.089	0.066
Aldebaran	Antares	170	-0.021	0.012

Exeunt

Noetica

Quotes through the centuries:

The more you know, the more you know you don't know.

- Aristotle

Truth does not change because it is, or is not, believed by a majority of the people.

- Giordano Bruno

Two truths cannot contradict one another.

- Galileo Galilei

Truth is ever to be found in the simplicity, and not in the multiplicity and confusion of things.

- Isaac Newton

We are in the gutter, but some of us are looking at the stars.

- Oscar Wilde

The world will not be destroyed by those who do evil, but by those who watch them without doing anything.

- Albert Einstein

Photons are very light.

- Geoffrey Mandula

Ya nevah unnerstan' anything until ya see it workin' on 2x2 matrices.

- Richard Feynman

There are no black holes - in the sense of regimes from which light can't escape to infinity. There are however apparent horizons which persist for a period of time.

- Stephen Hawking

Don't take me literally.

- Robert Fowler

ORION and TAO (and Obed) General Information (links)

May be found at the following URLs:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tamke-Allan_Observatory

<http://www.orioninc.org/>

<https://orionastronomy.wordpress.com>

<https://www.facebook.com/ORIONAstronomyTN/>

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/454645124557215>

<https://www.facebook.com/pages/Tamke-Allan%20Observatory/120477734665841>

<https://www.roanestate.edu/?349-Tamke-Allan-Observatory>

<https://www.roanestate.edu/pages/obs/index.htm>

<https://twitter.com/TAOremote>

ORIONastronomy@groups.io

Where is TAO?

334 Caney Creek Rd, Rockwood, TN 37854

N 35° 49' 57", W 84° 37' 04"; Alt. 324 m

Where is Obed?

Lilly Bluff Overlook

N 36° 06' 09", W 84° 43' 17"; Alt. 402 m

Nemo Bridge (on the bridge, E bank of Emory River)

N 36° 04' 07", W 84° 39' 43"; Alt. 268 m

Trapezium back issues online, at CERN's zenodo database:

A full CERN zenodo doi url is for example <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8219253>;
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Fin du journal

Why it is probably not a good idea to let your cat visit your observatory.

- Artwork by Sietske Barnes (ca. 2015)